

Transcendental Optimization in Geometric Programming via Power Series Approximations¹

Harpreet Singh

Research Scholar, Desh Bhagat University, Mandi Gobindgarh & Assistant Professor, Department of
Mathematics, Guru Nanak College, Budhlada, Mansa, Punjab, India

Sarabjit Kaur

Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics, Desh Bhagat University, Mandi Gobindgarh,
Punjab, India

sarabjitkaurchawla@gmail.com

Amanpreet Singh

Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics, GSSDGS Khalsa College, Patiala, Punjab, India

drapsingh25@gmail.com

Abstract

Transcendental Geometric Programming (TGP) is an extension of classical Geometric Programming that involves transcendental functions such as exponential, logarithmic, and trigonometric functions. In this paper, we consider a class of TGP problems in which the variables appear as exponential functions in both the objective function and the constraints. As a first step, we expand the exponential function using power series expansions, thereby reducing the Transcendental Geometric Programming Problem (TGPP) to a Standard Geometric Programming Problem (SGPP). Multiple cases of SGPP are then generated by truncating the power series to the first, second and third terms. Each of these cases is solved separately by converting the resulting SGPPs into linear programming problems using the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions and Taylor series approximations. This methodology leads us to derive the optimal solutions for the problem. Finally, Python programming is used to solve the problem.

Keywords

Transcendental Geometric Programming, Standard Posynomial Geometric Programming, Karush-Kuhn Tucker conditions, Taylor series expansion.

¹Address Author Correspondence to Harpreet Singh at preethar_singh@yahoo.co.in

Accepted: 14 May 2025 / Published online: 16 May 2025

© The Author(s), 2025; Paper ID: 400690; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15470667>

1. Introduction

Geometric programming is an optimization technique widely used to solve real-world applications across numerous fields under various scenarios. Its primary objective is to determine optimal solutions for both single-objective and multi-objective posynomial geometric programming problems. The concept was first introduced by Duffin, Peterson and Zener in 1967. Over time, several methods have been developed for solving posynomial geometric programming problems with significant contributions from Beightler et al. [1], Avriel et al. [2], and Duffin et al. [3].

In the past decade, geometric programming has gained significant attention from researchers. Several researchers, including Liu [4], Ojha et al. [5], and Mahapatra [6], have proposed solution procedures for determining optimal solutions for such problems.

Ojha and Biswal [7] formulated a method for solving multi-objective geometric programming problems (MOGPP) using the weighted mean method. Mousavi and Saraj [8] implemented a parametric approach, proposed by Mahapatra and Mandal [6], for multi-objective geometric programming problems with interval coefficients. A hybrid method was adopted by Ojha and Ota [9] to solve MOGPPs, integrating the ϵ -constraint method with the weighted mean method.

A dynamic approach was introduced by Oz et al. [10], in which the KKT conditions were applied to minimize the weighted objective function, followed by a first-order Taylor series approximation. Singh et al. [11] proposed a blended method in which the numerical approach proposed by Erzoy et al. [10] for MOGPP was applied to a single objective posynomial geometric programming problem with interval coefficient by initially transforming interval coefficient into single values using an interval-valued function.

Lidor et al. [12] introduced the concept of transcendental geometric programming problems, extending traditional geometric programming to handle problems involving transcendental functions. Their work provided fundamental principles for the formulation and solution of TGP problems, laying the foundations for further research in this domain.

In this paper, we consider a transcendental geometric programming problem in which the variables in both the objective function and the constraints are represented as exponential functions. In this type, the TGPP is first reduced to Standard GPP by expanding the exponential function into a power series. To analyze TGPP, we examine multiple cases by truncating the series to the first, second and third terms. Subsequently, we apply an alternative approach proposed by Erzoy et al. [10] to obtain the solution. The programming is done in Python, and a cloud-based Python IDE platform, Google Colab, is used to execute the programs.

2. Basic Terminology

2.1. Standard Posynomial Geometric Programming Problem

The Standard Posynomial Geometric Programming Problem is stated as:

$$\text{Minimize } f_0(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \prod_{j=1}^m x_j^{q_{i,j}}$$

Subject to
$$f_k(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{l_k} r_{ik} \prod_{j=i}^m x_j^{s_{ij}} \leq 1, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, k_0$$

$$x_j > 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

where the exponents q_{ij}, s_{ij} can take arbitrary real values where as the coefficients p_i, r_{ik} can assume positive real values.

2.2. Transcendental Geometric Programming Problem

The General form of Single Objective Transcendental Geometric Programming Problem can be stated as:

Minimize
$$f_0(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \prod_{j=i}^m x_j^{q_{ij}} g_0(t)$$

Subject to
$$f_k(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{l_k} q_i \prod_{j=i}^m x_j^{s_{ij}} g_j(t) \leq 1, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, k_0$$

$$x_j > 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

where the exponents q_{ij}, s_{ij} can take arbitrary real values, where as the coefficients p_i, q_i are assumed to be positive real numbers and $g_0(t), g_j(t)$ are functions of variable t , represented as transcendental functions such as exponential, logarithmic, and trigonometric functions.

3. Algorithm

The algorithm provides a systematic approach for solving optimization problems. The key steps for the algorithm are outlined below:

Step I: Problem Selection

Select an optimization problem where the variables appear as exponential terms.

Step II: Series Expansion

Expand the exponential function as a series and truncate it at different orders.

Step III: Formulation of Optimization problems

Use the truncated series obtained in Step II to form multiple versions of the optimization problems.

Step IV: Reformulation using Optimization conditions

Reformulate the problem at each truncation level obtained in Step III using Lagrange multipliers and the KKT conditions to derive the objective function and the corresponding constraints.

Step V: Linearization using Taylor series

Use Taylor series to convert the system of non-linear expressions into a linear system.

Step VI: Computational Implementation

Use Python Programming to compute the values of the objective function and the constraints at the initial feasible point. Execute the programs using Google Colab.

Step VII: Solution Verification

Verify whether the obtained solution satisfies the constraints. Evaluate the accuracy of different series truncations. If the approximation is not accurate, increase the number of terms in the exponential series and go to Step IV.

4. Numerical Example

The proposed structure of the algorithm is demonstrated with the help of an example. In this example, a problem of aforementioned type is considered, where a variable in both the objective function and the constraint appears as exponential terms. The problem was previously studied by G. Lidor et al. [12].

Problem:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} e^{-t}$$

Subject to

$$x_2^{-1} e^{2t} \leq 1 ,$$

$$x_1, x_2, t > 0$$

Expanding Exponential function in series:

Sub case I: Truncating Exponential Series upto 1st term:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2}$$

Subject to

$$x_2^{-1} \leq 1$$

$$x_1, x_2, t > 0$$

By introducing the slack variables, the above problem takes the form:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2}$$

Subject to

$$x_2^{-1} + \gamma_1^2 - 1 = 0$$

$$x_1, x_2, t > 0$$

Analogous to Lagrangian theorem and with the help of a multiplier (y , say), the objective function for the above problem can be defined as:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} - y(1 - x_2^{-1} - \gamma_1^2) \quad \dots (1)$$

Using KKT conditions, the above problem takes the form:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} \quad \dots (2)$$

Subject to

$$-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 t + t^{-2} = 0 \quad \dots (3)$$

$$2x_1^{-1} x_2 t - y x_2^{-2} = 0 \quad \dots (4)$$

$$x_1^{-1} x_2^2 - 2x_1 t^{-3} = 0 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$y(1 - x_2^{-1}) \geq 0 \quad \dots (6)$$

$$x_1, x_2, t, y > 0$$

Furthermore, using a first-order Taylor series expansion about any arbitrary feasible point, $X^0 (x_1^0, x_2^0, t^0, y^0)$, the above nonlinear mathematical programming problem with inequality constraints can be transformed into a linear programming problem as:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)]_{X^0} \approx [x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2}]_{X^0} + [-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 t + t^{-2}]_{X^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [2x_1^{-1} x_2 t]_{X^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [x_1^{-1} x_2^2 - 2x_1 t^{-3}]_{X^0} (t - t^0) \quad \dots (7)$$

Subject to

$$[-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 t + t^{-2}]_{X^0} + [2x_1^{-3} x_2^2 t]_{X^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [-2x_1^{-2} x_2 t]_{X^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 - 2t^{-3}]_{X^0} (t - t^0) = 0 \quad \dots (8)$$

$$[2x_1^{-1} x_2 t - y x_2^{-2}]_{X^0} + [-2x_1^{-2} x_2 t]_{X^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [2x_1^{-1} t + 2y x_2^{-3}]_{X^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [2x_1^{-1} x_2]_{X^0} (t - t^0) + [-x_2^{-2}]_{X^0} (y - y^0) = 0 \quad \dots (9)$$

$$[x_1^{-1} x_2^2 - 2x_1 t^{-3}]_{X^0} + [-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 - 2t^{-3}]_{X^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [2x_1^{-1} x_2]_{X^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [6x_1 t^{-4}]_{X^0} (t - t^0) = 0 \quad \dots (10)$$

$$[y(1 - x_2^{-1})]_{X^0} + [x_2^{-2} y]_{X^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [1 - x_2^{-1}]_{X^0} (y - y^0) \geq 0 \quad \dots (11)$$

Let us consider the random feasible point X^0 to be:

$$x_1^0 = 0.4, \quad x_2^0 = 1.8, \quad t^0 = 0.1, \quad y^0 = 1.5$$

Corresponding to point X^0 , the codes for the objective function (7) and the constraints (8) to (11) are written in Python given as below and executed on Google Colab.

For the purpose of computation, the initial variables x_1^0, x_2^0, t^0, y^0 are replaced by alternative variables $n1, n2, n3, m1$ while coding in Google colab.

Python code for objective function (7) & constraints (8) to (11):

```
from sympy import *
!pip install pulp
from pulp import *
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
# Create an object of a model
prob = LpProblem("Simple LP Problem", LpMinimize)
# Define the decision variables
x1 = LpVariable("x1", 0)
x2 = LpVariable("x2", 0)
t = LpVariable("t", 0)
y = LpVariable("y", 0)
n1=0.4
n2=1.8
```

```

n3=0.1
m1=1.5
a1 = symbols('a1')
a2 = symbols('a2')
a3 = symbols('a3')
minz=(((pow(n1,-1)*pow(n2,2)*n3)+(pow(n1,1)*pow(n3,-2)))+((-pow(n1,-2)*pow(n2,2)*n3)+(pow(n3,-2)))*(a1-n1))+((2*pow(n1,-1) *n2*n3)*(a2-n2))+(((pow(n1,-1)*pow(n2,2))-(2*n1*pow(n3,-3)))*(a3-n3))
smpl = simplify(minz)
smpl
c1=smpl.coeff(a1,1)
c2=smpl.coeff(a2,1)
c3=smpl.coeff(a3,1)
c4=smpl.subs([(a1,0),(a2,0),(a3,0)])
print(smpl)
print(c1,c2,c3,c4)
97.975*a1 + 0.9*a2 - 791.9*a3 + 79.19
97.97500000000 0.9000000000000 -791.9000000000 79.19000000000

# Define the objective function
prob += c1*x1+c2*x2+c3*t+c4
n1=0.4
n2=1.8
n3=0.1
m1=1.5
a1 = symbols('a1')
a2 = symbols('a2')
a3 = symbols('a3')
b1 = symbols('b1')
min=((-pow(n1,-2)*pow(n2,2)*n3)+(pow(n3,-2)))+((2*pow(n1,-3) * pow(n2,2)*n3)*(a1-n1))+((-2*pow(n1,-2)*n2*n3)*(a2-n2))+((-pow(n1,-2)*pow(n2,2))-(2*pow(n3,-3)))*(a3-n3))
smpl = simplify(min)
smpl
c1=smpl.coeff(a1,1)
c2=smpl.coeff(a2,1)
c3=smpl.coeff(a3,1)
c4=smpl.coeff(b1,1)
c5=smpl.subs([(a1,0),(a2,0),(a3,0),(b1,0)])
print(smpl)
print(c1,c2,c3,c4,c5)
10.125*a1 - 2.25*a2 - 2020.25*a3 + 300.0
10.1250000000 -2.2500000000 -2020.2500000000 0 300.0000000000
    
```

Define the constraints

```

prob += c1*x1+c2*x2+c3*t+c4*y+c5 == 0, "1st constraint"
n1=0.4
n2=1.8
n3=0.1
m1=1.5
a1 = symbols('a1')
a2 = symbols('a2')
a3 = symbols('a3')
b1 = symbols('b1')
min=(((2*pow(n1,-1)*pow(n2,1)*n3)-(m1*pow(n2,-2)))+((-2*pow(n1,-2)*pow(n2,1)*n3)*(a1-
n1))+(((2*pow(n1,-1)*n3)+(2*m1*pow(n2,-3)))*(a2-n2))+((2*pow(n1,-1)*pow(n2,1))*(a3-n3))+((-
pow(n2,-2))*(b1-m1)))
smpl = simplify(min)
smpl
c1=smpl.coeff(a1,1)
c2=smpl.coeff(a2,1)
c3=smpl.coeff(a3,1)
c4=smpl.coeff(b1,1)
c5=smpl.subs([(a1,0),(a2,0),(a3,0),(b1,0)])
print(smpl)
print(c1,c2,c3,c4,c5)
-2.25*a1 + 1.01440329218107*a2 + 9.0*a3 - 0.308641975308642*b1 - 0.925925925925926
-2.250000000000000 1.01440329218107 9.000000000000000
-0.308641975308642 -0.925925925925926
prob += c1*x1+c2*x2+c3*t+c4*y+c5 == 0, "2nd constraint"
n1=0.4
n2=1.8
n3=0.1
m1=1.5
a1 = symbols('a1')
a2 = symbols('a2')
a3 = symbols('a3')
b1 = symbols('b1')
min=(((pow(n1,-1)*pow(n2,2))-(2*n1*pow(n3,-3)))+(((pow(n1,-2)*pow(n2,2))-(2*pow(n3,-3)))*(a1-
n1))+((2*pow(n1,-1)*n2)*(a2-n2))+((6*pow(n1,1)*pow(n3,-4))*(a3-n3)))
smpl = simplify(min)
smpl
c1=smpl.coeff(a1,1)
c2=smpl.coeff(a2,1)

```

```
c3=smpl.coeff(a3,1)
c4=smpl.coeff(b1,1)
c5=smpl.subs([(a1,0),(a2,0),(a3,0),(b1,0)])
print(smpl)
print(c1,c2,c3,c4,c5)
-2020.25*a1 + 9.0*a2 + 24000.0*a3 - 2400.0
-2020.2500000000 9.0000000000 24000.0000000000 0 -2400.0000000000
prob += c1*x1+c2*x2+c3*t+c4*y+c5 == 0, "3rd constraint"
n1=0.4
n2=1.8
n3=0.1
m1=1.5
a1 = symbols('a1')
a2 = symbols('a2')
a3 = symbols('a3')
b1 = symbols('b1')
min=(((m1)-(m1*pow(n2,-1))))+((pow(n2,-2)*m1)*(a2-n2))+((1-pow(n2,-1))*(b1-m1)))
smpl = simplify(min)
smpl
c1=smpl.coeff(a1,1)
c2=smpl.coeff(a2,1)
c3=smpl.coeff(a3,1)
c4=smpl.coeff(b1,1)
c5=smpl.subs([(a1,0),(a2,0),(a3,0),(b1,0)])
print(smpl)
print(c1,c2,c3,c4,c5)
0.462962962962963*a2 + 0.444444444444444*b1 - 0.833333333333333
0 0.462962962962963 0 0.444444444444444 -0.833333333333333
prob += c1*x1+c2*x2+c3*t+c4*y+c5 >= 0, "4th constraint"
prob.solve()
1
# Print the results
print ("Status: ", LpStatus[prob.status])
Status: Optimal
for v in prob.variables():
    print (v.name, "=", v.varValue)
t = 0.15025757
x1 = 0.60207108
x2 = 1.1280526
y = 0.69994525
```

```
print ("The optimal value of the objective function is = ", value(prob.objective))
```

The optimal value of the objective function is = 20.2041917200000

The codes and the value of the main objective function corresponding to above set of values:

Objective function truncated upto 1st term:

```
from sympy import *  
x1=0.60207108  
x2=1.1280526  
t=0.15025757  
minz=((pow(x1,-1)*pow(x2,2)*t)+(pow(x1,1)*pow(t,-2)))  
smp1 = simplify(minz)  
smp1  
26.9846299854533
```

Original Objective function:

```
import math  
x1=0.57844803  
x2=1.3429723  
t=0.14729077  
minz=((pow(x1,-1)*pow(x2,2)*t)+(pow(x1,1)*pow(t,-2)*(math.exp(-t))))  
smp1 = simplify(minz)  
smp1  
23.4707874284599
```

The codes and the value of the constraints corresponding to above set of values:

Constraint truncated upto 1st term:

```
x2=1.1280526  
t=0.15025757  
minz=(pow(x2,-1))<=1  
smp1 = simplify(minz)  
smp1
```

True

Original Constraint:

```
import math  
x2=1.1280526  
t=0.15025757  
minz=(pow(x2,-1)*(math.exp(2*t)))<=1  
# smp1 = simplify(minz)  
# smp1  
minz  
False
```

Sub case II: Truncating Exponential series upto two terms:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} - x_1 t^{-1}$$

$$\text{Subject to } x_2^{-1} + 2x_2^{-1} t \leq 1$$

$$x_1, x_2, t > 0$$

By introducing the slack variables, the above problem takes the form:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} - x_1 t^{-1}$$

$$\text{Subject to } x_2^{-1} + 2x_2^{-1} t + \gamma_1^2 - 1 = 0$$

$$x_1, x_2, t > 0$$

Analogous to Lagrangian theorem and with the help of multipliers (y , say), the objective function for the above problem can be defined as:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} - x_1 t^{-1} - y(1 - x_2^{-1} - 2x_2^{-1} t - \gamma_1^2)$$

Using KKT conditions, the above problem takes the form:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} - x_1 t^{-1}$$

$$\text{Subject to } -x_1^{-2} x_2^2 t + t^{-2} - t^{-1} = 0$$

$$2x_1^{-1} x_2 t - y(x_2^{-2} + 2x_2^{-2} t) = 0$$

$$x_1^{-1} x_2^2 - 2x_1 t^{-3} + x_1 t^{-2} - y(-2x_2^{-1}) = 0$$

$$y(1 - x_2^{-1} - 2x_2^{-1} t) \geq 0$$

Further, using the first order Taylor's series expansion about any initial feasible point X^0 , the above system of non-linear mathematical programming problem with inequality constraints can be transformed into linear programming problem given as:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)]_{x^0} \approx [x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} - x_1 t^{-1}]_{x^0} + [-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 t + t^{-2} - t^{-1}]_{x^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [2x_1^{-1} x_2 t]_{x^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [x_1^{-1} x_2^2 - 2x_1 t^{-3} + x_1 t^{-2}]_{x^0} (t - t^0)$$

Subject to

$$[-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 t + t^{-2} - t^{-1}]_{x^0} + [2x_1^{-3} x_2^2 t]_{x^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [-2x_1^{-2} x_2 t]_{x^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 - 2t^{-3} + t^{-2}]_{x^0} (t - t^0) = 0$$

$$[2x_1^{-1} x_2 t - y(x_2^{-2} + 2x_2^{-2} t)]_{x^0} + [-2x_1^{-2} x_2 t]_{x^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [2x_1^{-1} t - y(-2x_2^{-3} - 4x_2^{-3} t)]_{x^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [2x_1^{-1} x_2 - 2yx_2^{-2}]_{x^0} (t - t^0) + [-x_2^{-2} - 2x_2^{-2} t]_{x^0} (y - y^0) = 0$$

$$[x_1^{-1} x_2^2 - 2x_1 t^{-3} + x_1 t^{-2} + 2yx_2^{-1}]_{x^0} + [-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 - 2t^{-3} + t^{-2}]_{x^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [2x_1^{-1} x_2 - 2yx_2^{-2}]_{x^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [6x_1 t^{-4} - 2x_1 t^{-3}]_{x^0} (t - t^0) + [2x_2^{-1}]_{x^0} (y - y^0) = 0$$

$$[y(1 - x_2^{-1} - 2x_2^{-1} t)]_{x^0} + [y(x_2^{-2} + 2x_2^{-2} t)]_{x^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [-2x_2^{-1} y]_{x^0} (t - t^0) [1 - x_2^{-1} - 2x_2^{-1} t]_{x^0} (y - y^0) \geq 0$$

Sub case III: Truncating Exponential series upto three terms:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} - x_1 t^{-1} + 0.5x_1$$

$$\text{Subject to } x_2^{-1} + 2x_2^{-1} t + 2t^2 x_2^{-1} \leq 1$$

$$x_1, x_2, t > 0$$

By introducing the slack variables, the above problem takes the form:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} - x_1 t^{-1} + 0.5 x_1$$

Subject to $x_2^{-1} + 2x_2^{-1} t + 2t^2 x_2^{-1} + \gamma_1^2 - 1 = 0$

$$x_1, x_2, t > 0$$

Analogous to Lagrangian theorem and with the help of a multiplier (y , say), the above problem can be defined as:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} - x_1 t^{-1} + 0.5 x_1 - y(1 - x_2^{-1} - 2x_2^{-1} t - 2x_2^{-1} t^2 - \gamma_1^2)$$

Using KKT conditions, the constraints for the above problem takes the form:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)] = x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} - x_1 t^{-1} + 0.5 x_1$$

Subject to $-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 t + t^{-2} - t^{-1} + 0.5 = 0$

$$2x_1^{-1} x_2 t - y(x_2^{-2} + 2x_2^{-2} t + 2t^2 x_2^{-2}) = 0$$

$$x_1^{-1} x_2^2 - 2x_1 t^{-3} + x_1 t^{-2} - y(-2x_2^{-1} - 4t x_2^{-1}) = 0$$

$$y(1 - x_2^{-1} - 2x_2^{-1} t - 2t^2 x_2^{-1}) \geq 0$$

Further, using the first order Taylor's series expansion about any initial feasible point X^0 , the above system of non-linear mathematical programming problem with inequality constraints can be transformed into linear programming problem given as:

$$\text{Min } [f(x,t)]_{X^0} \approx [x_1^{-1} x_2^2 t + x_1 t^{-2} - x_1 t^{-1} + 0.5 x_1]_{X^0} + [-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 t + t^{-2} - t^{-1} + 0.5]_{X^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [2x_1^{-1} x_2 t]_{X^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [x_1^{-1} x_2^2 - 2x_1 t^{-3} + x_1 t^{-2}]_{X^0} (t - t^0)$$

Subject to

$$[-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 t + t^{-2} - t^{-1} + 0.5]_{X^0} + [2x_1^{-3} x_2^2 t]_{X^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [-2x_1^{-2} x_2 t]_{X^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 - 2t^{-3} + t^{-2}]_{X^0} (t - t^0) = 0$$

$$[2x_1^{-1} x_2 t - y(x_2^{-2} + 2x_2^{-2} t + 2t^2 x_2^{-2})]_{X^0} + [-2x_1^{-2} x_2 t]_{X^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [2x_1^{-1} t - y(-2x_2^{-3} - 4x_2^{-3} t - 4t^2 x_2^{-3})]_{X^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [2x_1^{-1} x_2 - y(2x_2^{-2} + 4tx_2^{-2})]_{X^0} (t - t^0) + [-(x_2^{-2} + 2x_2^{-2} t + 2t^2 x_2^{-2})]_{X^0} (y - y^0) = 0$$

$$[x_1^{-1} x_2^2 - 2x_1 t^{-3} + x_1 t^{-2} - y(-2x_2^{-1} - 4tx_2^{-1})]_{X^0} + [-x_1^{-2} x_2^2 - 2t^{-3} + t^{-2}]_{X^0} (x_1 - x_1^0) + [2x_1^{-1} x_2 - y(2x_2^{-2} + 4tx_2^{-2})]_{X^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [6x_1 t^{-4} - 2x_1 t^{-3} - y(-4x_2^{-1})]_{X^0} (t - t^0) + [2x_2^{-1} + 4tx_2^{-1}]_{X^0} (y - y^0) = 0$$

$$[y(1 - x_2^{-1} - 2x_2^{-1} t - 2t^2 x_2^{-1})]_{X^0} + [y(x_2^{-2} + 2x_2^{-2} t + 2t^2 x_2^{-2})]_{X^0} (x_2 - x_2^0) + [y(-2x_2^{-1} - 4tx_2^{-1})]_{X^0} (t - t^0) + [1 - x_2^{-1} - 2x_2^{-1} t - 2t^2 x_2^{-1}]_{X^0} (y - y^0) \geq 0$$

Both the sub cases II & III are solved using the same initial point as in sub case I using the same mathematical tool. The results for the sub cases I, II & III are depicted in the following table.

Table 1

x_1	x_2	t	y	Solution of linear system	Solution of objective function		Constraint satisfaction	
					Expanded	Main	Expanded	Original
Truncating exponential series upto 1 st term								
0.6020 7108	1.128 0526	0.1502 5757	0.699 94525	20.2041917 200000	26.98462 99854533	23.2642109 084524	Satisfied	Not satisfied
Truncating exponential series upto 2 nd term								
0.5784 4803	1.342 9723	0.1472 9077	0.998 1667	16.5397105 462500	23.19525 55730187	23.4707874 284599	Satisfied	Satisfied
Truncating exponential series upto 3 rd term								
0.5817 2186	1.377 6544	0.1475 2778	1.035 3184	16.9715927 415000	23.55713 2632025	23.5433416 214088	Satisfied	Satisfied

5. Analysis of Results

The table presents the results of solving a TGPP while approximating an exponential objective function using a truncated series expansion. The key findings from the above table of results are as follows:

i. Solution of the Linear System:

With the successive inclusion of terms in the exponential series, the variables change their values but become more stable, with relative stabilization occurring while moving from the 2nd term to the 3rd term.

ii. Objective Function Behavior:

It is noted that the value of the expanded objective function decreases as more terms are added to the series whereas the original objective function shows a slight increasing trend but remains stable. This stabilization of values depicts that the approximation becomes more reliable with the addition of more terms which implies that the overall system is well-posed. As additional terms are included, the expanded and original functions begin to converge.

iii. Constraint Satisfaction and Feasibility:

When only 1st term of the exponential series is considered, the solution satisfies the constraint corresponding to expanded exponential series but not the original constraint. From the 2nd term onward, both constraints are satisfied, indicating that a higher-order expansion better adheres to the system's conditions.

iv. Convergence and Stability:

The values of the variables remain stable between the 2nd and 3rd term approximations, suggesting that the approximation is converging and the additional terms may not significantly improve the results. The

error introduced by truncating the series decreases as more terms are included. The rate of convergence suggests that a third order approximation may be sufficient for practical purposes.

6. Conclusion

With the inclusion of second and third terms, all constraints are satisfied, ensuring a feasible solution. It is observed that higher-order approximations are required to maintain feasibility in the system. As the objective function stabilizes after the 3rd term, adding more terms may not be computationally efficient. The results indicate convergence, as the solution and objective function values exhibit minimal changes beyond the third term and the rate of convergence is observed to be rapid between the first and second terms. After the second term, the rate of error reduction slows down, suggesting that the third-order approximation might be sufficient to obtain the accurate and computationally efficient results.

References

1. Beightler, C., & Phillips, D. (1976). *Applied Geometric Programming*. Wiley.
2. Avriel, M., Dembo, R., & Passy, U. (1975). Solution of Generalized Geometric Programs. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, Vol. 9.
3. Duffin, R.J., Peterson, E.L., and Zener, C. (1967). *Geometric Programming*, John Wiley and Sons, New York.
4. Liu, S.-T. (2006). Posynomial Geometric Programming with parametric uncertainty. *European journal of operational research*, 168, 345-353.
5. Ojha, A., & Biswal, K. (January 2010). posynomial geometric programming problems with multiple parameters. *Journal of computing*, vol. 2 (issue 1).
6. Mahapatra, G., & Mandal, T. (2012). Posynomial parametric geometric programming with interval valued coefficient. *J Optim Theory Appl*, 154, 120-132.
7. Ojha, A., & Biswal, K. (2010). Multi-objective Geometric Programming problem with weighted mean method. *International Journal of Computer science and Information security*, vol. 7 (no. 2).
8. Mousavi, Z., & Saraj, M. (2019). Multi-objective Geometric Programming with interval coefficients: A Parametric approach. *Earthline journal of Mathematical Sciences*, vol. 2 (no. 2), 395-407.
9. Ojha, A., & Ota, R. R. (2015). A Hybrid Method for Solving Multi-objective Geometric Programming Problem. *Int. J. Mathematics in Operational Research*, Vol. 7 (No. 2).
10. Oz, E., Guzel, N., & Alp, S. (2017). An Alternative Approach to the solution of Multi-Objective Geometric Programming Problem. *Open Journal of Optimization*, 6, 11-25.
11. Singh, H., & Singh, A. (2023). Estimating Solution of Posynomial Geometric Programming Problems having Interval Coefficients. *Journal for Educators, Teachers and Trainers*, 14 (6).
12. Lidor G., Wilde D.J. (1978). Transcendental Geometric Programs. *Journal of Optimization Theory and Applications*, 26, 77-96.